

Reactions of Fluorinated Isatin Derivatives with 2-Aminothiophenol

ANSHU DANDIA, SANGEETA KHANNA and KRISHNA C. JOSHI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 14 June 1990, accepted 26 July 1990

The role of fluorine incorporation in effecting the course of the reactions of fluorinated isatin derivatives (1a-c) with 2-aminothiophenol (2) has been investigated in dry xylene in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride and in the process some new fluorine containing 2-(2-oxo-2H-1,4-benzothiazine-3-yl)aniline (3), indolo[2,3-b][1,4]-benzothiazine (4), N-[2-(3,4-dihydro-2-oxo-2H-1,4-benzothiazin-3-yl)phenyl]acetamide (5) and spiro[benzothiazole-2(3H)-3'-indol]-2'(1'H)-ones (6) have been synthesised. Characterisation of all the compounds has been done on the basis of elemental analyses and ir, ^1H , ^{19}F , ^{13}C nmr and mass spectral data.

In an attempt to synthesise some pharmacologically active fluorine containing indole derivatives¹, we have investigated the reaction of fluorinated isatin derivatives with 2-aminothiophenol (2) as fluorine incorporation in heterocycles may cause changes in electronic environment and effect the course of reaction besides influencing biological activity².

A literature survey revealed scanty reports^{3,4} on the title reaction. Literature³ reports the formation of 2-(acetyl-amino)-N-(2-mercaptophenyl)- α -[(2-mercaptophenyl)amino]benzeneacetamide and 2-(2-benzothiazolyl)aniline in ethanol and N-[2-(2-oxo-2H-1,4-benzothiazin-3-yl)phenyl]acetamide in acetic acid. However, during our studies⁴ on the reactions of aminothiophenol and non-fluorinated isatin derivatives, results, at variance from those reported earlier, have been obtained indicating a possible

role of substituent at indole nitrogen during condensation reaction.

Prompted by the wide variety of biological activities of thiazole and benzothiazines⁵ and the scanty information available in literature on their fluorinated analogs, we have now investigated the reaction of 2-aminothiophenol with fluorinated isatins in dry xylene in presence of anhydrous ZnCl_2 wherein observed a significant role of fluorine during the reaction. Fluoroisatins are found to be less reactive (where reaction did not occur at room temperature) unlike in their non-fluorinated analogs⁴. During the reaction of 2-aminothiophenol (2) with 5-fluoroisatin (1a), the formation of two products was indicated by tlc and these were separated by column chromatography. The yellow compound (3) showed ir absorptions at 3 460, 3 310 (NH_2) and 1 628 cm^{-1} (CO). The presence of carbonyl group was confirmed by ^{13}C nmr where the characteristic peaks were observed at δ 168.08 (CO), 159.02 (C=N), 153.90 (C-F), 149.25 (C-10'), 144.28 (C-9'), 133.40 (C-5), 126.49 (C-6'), 125.42 (C-3), 122.55 (C-1), 119.75 (C-4'), 118.68 (C-8'), 118.26 (C-2) and 115.46 (C-6). However, the low frequency shift noticed in its ir spectrum may be explained due to the field effect of the non-bonding p-electrons of amino group. Further, in the mass spectrum, although molecular ion peak was not observed, the highest peak was observed at m/z 244 (100%) probably by the loss of neutral CO molecule. Other peaks were observed at m/z 243 ($M^+ - \text{CHO}$) (10.2%), 220 ($244 - \text{N}_2$) (16%), 218 ($244 - \text{CN}$), 146 ($M^+ - \text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{FNO}$) (15.3%), 109 ($M^+ - \text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{NOS}$) (28%) and 94 ($M^+ - \text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{OS}$) (12%). On the basis of elemental and spectral studies, compound 3 was identified as 4-fluoro-2-(2-oxo-2H-1,4-benzothiazine-3-yl)aniline⁴. Another red compound (4) was recovered from benzene-ethyl acetate (2 : 3) fraction. Its spectrum showed complete disappearance of carbonyl absorption and strong absorptions were observed at 1 590 and 1 490 cm^{-1} (C=N). ^1H nmr spectrum showed multiplets at δ 6.42-7.96 due to aromatic

Scheme 1

protons. The mass spectrum showed molecular ion peak at m/z 254 (100%). Other peaks were observed at 178 ($M^+ - C_6H_4$) (7.9%), 108 ($M^+ - C_8H_4NS$) (99.4%), 82 (108-CN) (26.8%) and 69 (82-CH) (48%). On the basis of the spectral data, compound **4** was identified as the condensed compound 9-fluoroindolo[2,3-*b*][1,4]benzothiazine. Methyl derivative of indolobenzothiazine synthesised by another route⁶, was unstable and rapidly converted into spiro compound in ethanol in the presence of air whereas the fluorinated indolobenzothiazin (**4**) was found to be quite stable and could not be converted into spiro compound even on refluxing in ethanol. Spiro compound **6** was not obtained in this case while it was the major product in the reaction of non-fluorinated isatin ($R=R'=H$).

In case of the reaction of 5-fluoro-1-acetylisatin (**1b**) and 2-aminothiophenol, no reaction occurred at room temperature as observed in case of non-fluorinated analog⁴. In contrast to the earlier literature report, deacetylation process was observed in this case. Two compounds were obtained which were separated by column chromatography. A yellow compound (**3**), recovered from the petroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1) fraction, was found to be identical to compound **3**, obtained from 5-fluoroisatin by tlc, m.m.p., co-ir and spectral studies. Another white compound which was obtained in the benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) fraction showed characteristic ir bands at 3 380 (NH), 3 290 (NH), 3 020 (aliphatic CH), 1 690 (COCH₃), 1 660 cm⁻¹ (CO). ¹H nmr spectrum showed peaks at δ 2.10 (3H, s, NHCOCH₃), 4.90 (1H, s, benzylic CH), 6.23-7.01 (7H, m, ArH), 9.15 (1H, s, NH) and 10.15 (1H, s, NH). ¹³C nmr spectrum exhibited the characteristic peaks at δ 171.12 (COCH₃), 167.12 (CO), 149.22 (C-F), 136.92-124.26 (10 aromatic carbon), 119.23 (C₂ of phenyl acetamide), 79.80 (benzylic CH) and 23.57 (CH₃). Further, the mass spectrum of this compound showed molecular ion peak at m/z 316 (M^+) (46.7) and some other peaks at m/z 273 ($M^+ - COCH_3$) (38.6%), 245 (273-CO) (20.1%), 150 (245-C₆H₄F) (13%) and 92 (273-C₈H₈N₂OS) (100%). In contrast to 1-acetylisatin, the shift of methyl protons of **5** to δ 2.10 as compared to 2.66 and alongwith ¹H and ¹³C nmr data for benzylic CH, confirms the opening of N-C₂ bond and reduction of azomethine double bond. On the basis of the above observations, compound **5** was identified as 4-fluoro-*N*-[2-(3,4-dihydro-2-oxo-2*H*-1,4-benzothiazine-3-yl)phenyl]acetamide.

Reaction of 5-fluoro/6-fluoro-1-methylisatin (**1c**/**1d**) with 2-aminothiophenol (**2**) yielded exclusively the spiro compound **6a**/**6b** with improved yield (50/55%)⁴. However, the spiro compound was not obtained by earlier workers³. Ir spectrum of this compound exhibited characteristic absorptions at 3 210 (NH), 3 000-2 980 (CH₃) and 1 700 cm⁻¹ (C=O). ¹H nmr spectrum showed peaks at δ 3.01 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.96 (1H, s, thiazole NH), 6.23-7.62 (7H, m, ArH) and mass spectrum showed molecular

ion peak at m/z 286 (M^+) (30.3%) with the highest peak at 258 (100%) due to the loss of neutral CO.

The presence and position of fluorine were confirmed by ¹⁹F nmr using hexafluorobenzene as external standard. Fluorine attached to the phenyl ring was observed at δ -105 to -107 ppm (**3** and **5**) and the single fluorine attached to the indole ring in compounds (**4** and **6**) was observed at δ -113 to -116 ppm.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer and Fourier-ir were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1800 spectrophotometer in KBr pellet. ¹H and ¹⁹F nmr spectra were recorded on a Jeol FX 90 Q spectrometer using trifluoroacetic acid, deuterated dimethyl sulphoxide and deuterated chloroform as solvents at 89.55 MHz and 84.25 MHz respectively; tetramethylsilane was used as internal standard for ¹H nmr and hexafluorobenzene as external standard for ¹⁹F nmr. ¹³C nmr spectra were recorded on a Jeol FX 90 Q spectrometer using deuterated dimethylsulphoxide as solvent at 22.49 MHz. Mass spectra were recorded on Kratos 30 and 50 mass spectrometers. The mixture of products were separated by column chromatography using silica gel. All compounds were homogeneous on tlc in various solvent systems. Fluorinated isatin derivatives (**1a-d**) were synthesised by literature methods⁷.

*Reaction of 5-fluoroisatin (1a) with 2-aminothiophenol (2). Synthesis of 4-fluoro-2-(2-oxo-2H-1,4-benzothiazin-3-yl) aniline (3) and 9-fluoroindolo[2,3-*b*][1,4]benzothiazine (4):* A mixture of 5-fluoroisatin (**1a**; 0.01 mol) and 2-aminothiophenol (**2**; 0.012 mol) was refluxed in presence of dry xylene in anhydrous zinc chloride for 16 h. The formation of two products was indicated by tlc which were separated by column chromatography. A yellow compound, obtained in the petroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1) fraction was identified as **3**. Another red compound was recovered from benzene-ethyl acetate (2 : 3) fraction, which was identified as the condensed product (**4**): compound **3** (30%), m.p. 115°; **4** (20%), m.p. 175°.

Reaction of 1-acetyl-5-fluoroisatin (1b) with 2-aminothiophenol (2). Synthesis of 4-fluoro-N-[2-(3,4-dihydro-2-oxo-2H-1,4-benzothiazin-3-yl)phenyl]acetamide (5) and 4-fluoro-2-(2-oxo-2H-1,4-benzothiazin-3-yl)aniline (3): A mixture of 1-acetyl-5-fluoroisatin (0.01 mol) and 2-aminothiophenol (0.012 mol) was refluxed for 10 h. The two compounds, as indicated by tlc, were separated by column chromatography. The yellow compound obtained from the petroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1) fraction was found to be identical with 4-fluoro-2-(2-oxo-2*H*-1,4-benzothiazin-3-yl)aniline (**3**) obtained from isatin. Another white compound, recovered from the benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) fraction, was identified as **5**: compound **3** (40%), m.p. 115°; **5** (25%), m.p. 245°.

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	ν_{max} cm^{-1}	1H nmr δ ppm	^{19}F nmr δ ppm	^{13}C nmr δ ppm	m/z (%)
3	3 460, 3 310 (NH ₂), 1 628 (CO)	6.03–7.45 (m, 7-ArH)	-105.80(s)	168.08(CO), 159.02(C=N), 153.90(C-F), 149.25(C-10'), 144.28(C-9'), 133.40(C-5), 126.49(C-6'), 125.42(C-3), 122.55(C-1), 121.48(C-7'), 119.75(C-4'), 118.68(C-8'), 118.26(C-2), 115.46(C-6)	244(M ⁺ -CO)(100), 243(M ⁺ -CHO)(10.2), 220(244-N ₂)(16), 218(244-CN)(23), 146(M ⁺ -C ₆ H ₅ FN ₂ O) (15.3), 109(M ⁺ - C ₆ H ₅ NOS)(28), 254(M ⁺)(100), 178(M ⁺ -C ₆ H ₄)(7.9), 108(M ⁺ -C ₆ H ₄ NS)(99.4), 82(108-C=N)(26.8), 69(82-CH)(48) 316(M ⁺)(46.7), 273(M ⁺ -COCH ₃)(38.6), 245(273-CO)(20.1), 150(245-C ₆ H ₅ F)(13), 93(273-C ₆ H ₅ N ₂ OS)(100)
4	1 600, 1 590 (C=N, C=C)	6.42–7.96 (m, 7-ArH)	-113.20(s)	—	—
5	3 380 (NH), 3 290 (NH), 1 690 (COCH ₃), 1 660 (CO)	2.10 (s, COCH ₃), 4.90 (s, CH), 6.23–7.91 (m, 7-ArH) 9.15 (s, NH), 10.15 (s, NH)	-106.02(s)	171.12(COCH ₃), 167.13(CO), 149.22(C-F), 136.92–124.26 (11-aromatic C), 79(benzylic CH), 23.57(CH ₃)	—
6a	3 210 (NH), 1 700 (CO), 1 600	3.01 (s, CH ₃) 5.96 (s, thiazole NH), 6.23–7.62 (m, 7-ArH)	-1 6.23(s)	—	286(M ⁺)(30.3%), 258(M ⁺ -CO)(100)
6b	3 200 (NH), 1 710 (CO), 1 600	3.12 (s, CH ₃), 5.94 (s, thiazole NH), 6.4–7.8 (m, 7-ArH)	-114 (s)	—	—

Synthesis of 5-fluoro/6-fluoro-1-methyl-spiro[benzothiazole-2(3H),3'-indol]-2'(1'H)-one (4a/4b): A mixture of 5-fluoro/6-fluoro-1-methylindole-2,3-dione (1c/1d; 0.01 mol) and 2-aminothiophenol (2) (0.012 mol) in dry xylene in the presence of anhydrous zinc chloride was refluxed for 10 h. The supernatant liquid on concentration yielded the solid compounds: 4a (50%), m.p. 232°; 4b (55%), m.p. 240°.

Analytical and spectral data for all the compounds are listed in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS*

Isatin	Compds. obtained	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1a	3	115	30	C ₁₄ H ₉ FN ₂ OS
	4	175	20	C ₁₄ H ₇ FN ₂ S
1b	3	115	40	C ₁₄ H ₉ FN ₂ OS
	5	245	25	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ FN ₂ O ₂ S
1c	6a	232	50	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ FN ₂ OS
1d	6b	240	55	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ FN ₂ OS

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.D.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. K. C. JOSHI, R. JAIN and S. ARORA, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 1989, **42**, 14; K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and R. GUPTA, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 1988, **38**, 153; K. C. JOSHI, A. DANDIA and N. AHMED, *Heterocycles*, 1986, **24**, 2479.
2. "Fluorine Chemistry Reviews", ed. PAUL TARRANT, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1974, Vols. I-VII; R. FILLER, *Chem. Tech.*, 1974, **4**, 752; "Organic Fluorine Chemistry", eds. W. A. SHAPERS and C. M. SHARTS, W. A. BENJAMIN, New York, 1969; K. C. JOSHI, A. DANDIA and S. KHANNA, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1989, **26**, 1397; K. C. JOSHI, A. DANDIA and S. BHAGAT, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 1990, **43**, 169.
3. B. S. JOSHI, N. VISHWANATHAN and M. A. LIKHATE, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1989, **93**, 589.
4. S. KHANNA, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Rajasthan, 1989.
5. K. ISHINGURO, W. C. TAYL, R. J. DELOVENZO and A. C. SARTORELLI, *J. Cell Physiol.*, 1987, **131**, 226; B. S. REDDY and M. DARBARWAV, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 377; R. A. NICOLAUS, E. RAMUNDO, M. DIROSA and P. PERSICO, *Farmaco Ed. Sci.*, 1980, **35**, 333 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, **93**, 132429).
6. A. H. JACKSON, D. N. JOHNSTON and P. O. R. SHANON, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Comm.*, 1975, **22**, 911.
7. Y. Q. YEN, N. P. BUU-HOI and N. D. XUONG, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 185; P. W. SADLER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 169; G. TACCONI, P. P. RIGHETTI and G. DESIMONI, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1973, **315**, 339.